

CST4ALL

Support to the Activities of the Concentrated Solar Thermal Technology Area of the SET Plan

CST4ALL Industry Workshop on the hybridisation of Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies (CST) with geothermal

Date	10 March 2025
Time	10:00 – 13:00 CET
Online event	Microsoft Teams
Registration link	Available via CST4ALL website or Microsoft Teams

Draft Agenda

- 10:00 Welcome and introduction to CST4ALL project and webinar objectives**
Konstantinos Genikomsakis – *European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (ESTELA)*
Hande Eryilmaz – *ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications*
- 10:10 Message from the European Commission**
Elisabeth Schellmann – *DG for Energy, European Commission*
- 10:15 Keynote presentations on hybridisation possibilities of CST and geothermal**
Diego Caro Pegalajar – *ACCIONA Industrial*
Dario Bonciani – *Consortium for the Development of Geothermal Areas (COSVIG)*
Ahmet Lokurlu – *Soliterm Group GmbH*
Q&A
- 11:15 Live poll**
- 11:20 Break**
- 11:30 Round table: Industrial maturity of technologies, bankability of projects, regional specific conditions, necessary skills, market potential, manufacturing facilities in Europe and expected R&I contributions**
Moderator:
Derek Baker – *ODTÜ-GÜNAM Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications*
Participants:
Cristina Trueba – *Concentrated Solar Thermal Technologies Implementation Working Group (CST IWG)*

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101075408.

Simona De Iuliis – *Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA)*

Diego Caro Pegalajar – *ACCIONA Industrial*

Ahmet Lokurlu – *Soliterm Group GmbH*

Dario Bonciani – *Consortium for the Development of Geothermal Areas (COSVIG)*

Sanjeev Kumar – *European Geothermal Energy Council (EGEC)*

12:50 Wrap-up and conclusions

Peter Heller – *German Aerospace Center (DLR)*

13:00 End of workshop

ETIP Geothermal

This CST4ALL project event is organised with the support of the European Technology & Innovation Platform on Geothermal (ETIP-Geothermal).

CST4ALL Coordinator

DLR Deutsches Zentrum
für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.
in der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft

DLR: Deutsches Zentrum Fuer Luft - Und Raumfahrt EV (DE)

CST4ALL Partners

CIEMAT: Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas (ES)

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (IT)

ESTELA: European Solar Thermal Electricity Association (BE)

GUNAM: Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications (TR)

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